

Violation of Freedom of Speech and Expression: A Critical Study on the Arrest and Detention of the Indian Journalist, Sidheeq Kappan

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Abstract

This research paper aims at exploring the violation of freedom of speech and expression, a fundamental right incorporated in the constitution of India as well as various other constitutions worldwide. The study focuses on the importance of Article 19(1) (a) that covers the freedom of speech and expression; wherein which press freedom also adheres to. This paper analyzes an instance of violation of the same, highlighting the risk factor and safety implications that journalists and media houses across the world face. Through a qualitative approach incorporating content analysis and case study analysis, the paper aims to provide a comprehensive understanding of the dynamics involved in the violation of speech and expression rights. The findings of the study include the prevalence of serious anti- democratic issues, a rise in unjust court proceedings and transformation of India into a ground for communal riots, thus diminishing the existence of democratic values.

Keywords: *Violation, Democracy, Freedom, Media, Speech, Expression.*

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Introduction

The Indian Constitution

The Constitution of India is the supreme law of India. The Constitution is a comprehensive document that outlines the framework of the Indian government, its principles, and the rights and duties of its citizens.

Article 19 1(a)

The right related to the media is the freedom of speech and expression [article 19 (1) (a)] and the right to life and personal property (Article 21,25). The right to freedom of speech and expression involves the right to assemble, right to association, right to movement, right to residence and right to profession. This article implies that every citizen of the country has the right to express their views and opinions. It is not just the case of words of mouth, but also the right to write, draw and make films (Bonotti & Seglow, 2021).

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Freedom of the Press

The role of media in a democracy is as crucial as that of the politicians and should never be underestimated. The media can play a positive role in democracy only if there is an enabling environment that allows them to do so. They need the requisite skills for the kind of in-depth reporting that a new democracy requires. There should also be mechanisms to ensure they are held accountable to the public and that ethical and professional standards are upheld. Media independence is guaranteed if media organizations are financially viable, free from intervention of media owners and the state, and operate in a competitive environment. The Media should also be accessible to as wide a segment of society as possible.

Freedom of Press is implicit in the freedom of expression forming the backbone of political liberty and proper functioning of the democracy. The decline in Press freedom reveals a dangerous situation in the functioning of media and democracy in India. The condition of the press in India is more often attributed to the vulnerabilities of Indian democracy and the attitude of the political leadership. The media's political bias or absence of independent journalism are major areas of concern. Blatant political bias and association with feudal and religious forces define the nature of media nowadays. This could be the primary reason behind the erosion of democratic institutions like the media in the country.

Arrest of Sidheeq Kappan

Sidheeq Kappan is an Indian Journalist from Kerala who was arrested under false allegations in October 2020. He was charged under the Unlawful Activities Prevention Act. Three men who accompanied him that day were also accused of the same offense. He was released from jail on 02 February 2023 after spending 27 months in jail. In 2021, the Enforcement Directorate filed another case against him under the Prevention of the Money Laundering Act. The central agency said that Kappan received money from the political party Popular Front of India (PFI) to "incite riots" after claiming that he is a member of the party.

He was arrested in Uttar Pradesh on his way to investigate the Hathras gang rape case where a 19-year-old Dalit woman was allegedly gang raped and later killed. After being arrested, he was mentally and physically tortured by the police in jail, with no food and proper medication.

On being released on bail from a Lucknow prison on February 02 2023, Kappan told the media that he had no idea why he was implicated wrongly in a case and jailed for 27 months. That he has been only released on bail and not acquitted of all charges against him must make it clear that it may be quite a while before he can hope to completely prove his innocence. Siddique Kappan's loss of liberty for 846 days shows that our liberty too can be snatched by the State for no reason. "Anyone who is against the government is labeled as a terrorist", he told the media soon after his release. A close look at Kappan's legal battle since his arrest would show that the legal presumption of innocence till proven guilty has been turned upside down in his case, for no fault of his.

Press freedom activists stated that Kappan's arrest creates a fear that India is becoming unsafe for journalists. The violence against journalists, the politically corrupted media and the concentration of media ownership indicates that press freedom is in crisis, in the world's largest democracy.

In this context, there are many people all over the world who struggle to have full access to freedom of expression for a wide range of reasons including poverty, discrimination and cultural pressures. The right to speak your mind freely on important issues in society, access information and hold powers plays a vital role in a healthy development process of any society.

An effort has been made to answer the following questions by the end of the present study:

1. What is the concept, scope and meaning of Freedom of Speech and Expression under Article 19(1)(a) of the Indian Constitution?
2. Is the violation of freedom of speech and expression of journalists, a hindrance to the democratic functioning of a nation?

3. Are journalists being tortured based on their identity (the community to which they belong, their religion or personal life) rather than their identity as a media person?

Review of Literature

India is a democracy and citizens have a constitutional right to exercise the freedom of expression, which can be enforced through the Indian court system. Indian Constitution aims to ensure freedom of speech and expression to ensure a free and equal society. The judiciary has identified restrictions that can be imposed, but has found that governmental interference with this right must also be brought under control. Freedom of expression is one of the most important human rights.

Violation of Press Freedom

Journalists around the world face countless threats every day, from kidnapping, torture and arbitrary detention to disinformation campaigns and harassment, especially on social media. Female journalists are particularly at risk. A record number of journalists were imprisoned in 2020, according to the Commission to Protect Journalists (CPJ).

(The Committee to Protect Journalists is an independent, non-profit organization that fights for press freedom around the world.)

The safety of journalists is a top concern, and killings and attacks on journalists who cover sensitive issues are very common. Hate speech against journalists shared and spread on social media targets journalists who use social media. Corporate and political forces have overwhelmed much of the media, both print and visual, leading to the destruction of self-interest and liberty. Media freedom has deteriorated across the globe over the past decade. The threats to global media freedom are real and alarming in themselves, but their impact on the state of democracy makes them truly dangerous.

Articles on Freedom of Speech and Expression

“Freedom of Speech and Expression as a Fundamental Right in India and the Test of Constitutional Regulations: The Constitutional Perspective.”

This article deals with the importance of freedom of speech and expression, constitutional position of this freedom, its position in India, its scope, freedom of press and constitutional regulation of freedom of speech and expression. Freedom of speech and expression is guaranteed by the Indian Constitution as a fundamental right. The real question is whether you get a warranty. Law provides all theoretical rights, but theoretical rights do not necessarily provide all guarantees (Raza, 2016).

“Social media and Freedom of Speech and Expression: Challenges before the Indian law.”

The above article discusses what is social media, types of social media, freedom of speech and expression, restrictions on freedom of speech and expression, Censoring social media, cyber laws and IT Act, 2000 (Tiwari, Ghosh, 2014).

Freedom of press

This article attempts to understand the concept from British times to the present: the role of the press in shaping people's thoughts and ideas, and freedoms and restrictions past and present. It describes the practicality of the existence of such freedoms in these modern times, including the times of the coronavirus pandemic, and finally attempts to grasp the current role of government in relation to press freedom (Krishnakumar, 2021).

“A study on freedom of press in India: With reference to Article 19”

The article deals with the importance of a free and independent press and the ways by which media can influence the public in a democracy like India. The various ways through which press freedom is enjoyed in our nation is a matter of discussion here (Mugundhan, 2018).

Online Newspaper Sources

The updates of the Hathras gang rape case, which Sidheeq Kappan went to investigate and report (Ara, 2020).

The latest news on Sidheeq Kappan regarding his release. The statements he gave to the media about the violation of his basic rights as an individual, journalist and a prisoner is what is discussed in the news story (Venkatesan, 2023).

The story on the release of Sidheeq Kappan, after two years (Sidhique, 2023).

Story on the safety of journalists and the problems they face, showing the statistics of decline of media freedom.

Six years after the statement made by PM Modi in 2014 that what is a democracy without press freedom, many believe that India's democracy appears to be undermining as the continued assault on press freedom. Last year, India fell two places to 142nd in the Global Press Freedom Index of 180 countries compiled annually by Reporters Without Borders. For a country that often boasts of a vibrant and competitive media, this is flattering (Biswas, 2021).

Research Gap

Despite the presence of extensive literature on Freedom of Speech and Expression, there exists a gap in exploring the possibilities of violation citizens and journalists in particular face and how it disturbs the democratic set up of a country like India. Also, there are limited research done specifically to address the unsafe working conditions of journalists in India. Though rapid growth in technology paves way for advanced digital journalism and communication, the intensity of suppression is more based on the identity of citizens.

Research Objectives

- To analyze the importance of Article 19(1)(A) with respect to press freedom.
- To study how violation of press freedom causes hindrance to the effective functioning of a democracy.
- To examine how speech and expression violation is evident in the arrest of Sidheeq Kappan?

Methodology

To study the provisions under article 19(1)(a), an extensive study of the concept, meaning and analysis of the Indian Constitution and the above-mentioned article is done. This study aims to see the validation and implementation of the Freedom of speech and expression. The information is collected from various sources.

Similarly, to prove the provisions and implementation of the freedom of speech and expression, case studies are being referred to and are studied thoroughly. Here, the arrest of the journalist, Sidheeq Kappan is taken as the case study to prove the violation of freedom of speech and expression.

Qualitative study is chosen because it aims to produce contextual, real- world knowledge about the behaviors, social structures, and shared beliefs of people.

Existing data is also used for reference. The materials analyzed are newspaper reports, online sources of the case study and the associated incidents. For example, the arrest of Sidheeq

Kappan is reported by many newspapers and channels. They are compared and studied. Similarly, the arrest is associated with the Hathras gang rape case. So, this incident, its media coverage, worldwide attention- all are studied. The social problems related with both the incidents are also studied. Finally, the connection of this case with

violation of freedom of speech and expression is analyzed.

Although there has been some progress from the time when 'freedom of the media' can be estimated, the situation today is not very good. There have been lots of cases of hate crimes, false accusations, trials due to wrongful portrayal and fake news in the recent years. As of 2021, 6 journalists have been killed because of their work. India is among the top 4 countries with the greatest number of deaths on record. Whether it is on job or off the job, they have been targeted and attacked due to their work.

As direct analysis is very important in the study, Content analysis is being used as the method of analysis in this study through which the importance of freedom of speech and expression, its provisions, restrictions, violation, and cases that portray the violation is understood by going through different contents and cases that is available. This will help to have knowledge on the possibilities and to check whether it has given a strict implementation under the Indian Constitution and to examine how flexible and democratic is the constitution and the laws mentioned in it. Also, studying different case studies related to the violation of article 19(1)(a) will help to position the democratic norms followed by India in the context of free speech.

Content Analysis

This study uses content analysis which includes the study of:

- News articles
- Web content and social media posts
- Photos
- Interviews

Data Analysis

This research paper deals with the study of violation of article 19(1) (a) in India in the light of the arrest of the Indian journalist from Kerala, Sidheeq Kappan. The method of analysis used is qualitative analysis. Content analysis is used to elaborately study the subject.

Article 19(1)(a) states that "everyone has the right to freedom of opinion and expression; this right includes freedom to hold opinions without interference and to seek, receive and impart information and ideas through any media and regardless of frontiers."

However, this fundamental human right is frequently violated across the world, often by governments and those in positions of power who seek to suppress dissenting voices or control the narrative. Such violations can take many forms, including censorship, harassment, imprisonment, or even violence.

Censorship

One of the powerful entities that censor information, news, and opinion is the government. They select them because they are not in their interests as well as they are facing these autocracies. This can take many forms, from internet censorship to press restrictions, book banning, and even imprisonment or execution of journalists who report on sensitive topics. We can consider the example of China too. Here, the government imposes very strict controls on free expression. Internet and social media are both affected, with the former being used to block access to websites from foreign countries and the latter being used to censor material that is anti-policies to the ruling party. Likewise, in Saudi Arabia, the media is only free when the government allows it. This country uses These media outlets for example the state ones. They can publish material about freedom and liberties and then suddenly the same material gets censored for insufficient reasoning.

Another way to violate Article 19(1)(a) is with threats and intimidation. This can be from cyberbullying to physical assault on journalists or activists. Those who voice their opinions against the authorities or strong people may face threats, intimidation or even violence, with the specific intention of keeping them quiet and a general discouragement of others from speaking up. Nowadays, the methods employed by

governments and other powerful entities to harass or punish individuals who express dissenting views are mostly legal or administrative, like introducing fines, revoking licenses, or detaining individuals on false charges, among others.

Article 19(1)(a) is a fundamental human right that is essential for the functioning of a free and democratic society. But it is frequently violated by governments and other powerful entities that seek to control the narrative or suppress dissenting voices. Censorship, harassment, and manipulation of information are just a few of the ways in which this right can be violated, often with serious consequences for those who dare to speak out. It is therefore essential that individuals and organizations continue to fight for the protection of this right, to ensure that all voices can be heard and that the truth can be uncovered.

Violation of Article 19(1)(A) in the Context of the Arrest of Sidheeq Kappan

The Siddique Kappan case is related to the whereabouts and the detention of the journalists who were on their way to investigate the Hathras gangrape case. Due to some unforeseen reasons, they were taken into custody in the state of Uttar Pradesh, India in October, 2020. Kappan was arrested by the Uttar Pradesh police along with three others and was charged under various sections of the Unlawful Activities Prevention Act (UAPA). Being an oppressive law, the UAPA allows the arrest of persons without the bail limit of not more than 180 days; therefore, it has been criticized for its misuse in the suppression of the free speech of individuals and the press and the direct targeting of journalists and activists.

Kappan, who was working for the Malayalam news portal Azhimukham, was travelling to Hathras to report on the gangrape and murder of a Dalit woman. He was arrested at a toll plaza on the Delhi-Uttar Pradesh border and charged with sedition, promoting enmity between different groups, and under the UAPA. The Uttar Pradesh police claimed that Kappan and the others were part of a larger conspiracy to create unrest and disturb the peace in the state. However, there was no evidence to support these allegations, and Kappan and his colleagues were denied bail. The arrest and detention of Kappan drew widespread condemnation from journalists and human rights activists, who saw it as an attempt to silence independent reporting and intimidate journalists from reporting on sensitive issues.

The case went to the Supreme Court of India, which initially granted Kappan a bail on humanitarian grounds as he was reportedly suffering from various health issues. However, the Uttar Pradesh police opposed his release and filed an affidavit claiming that Kappan was part of a larger conspiracy to incite violence and disrupt public order. In March 2021, the Supreme Court rejected Kappan's bail application, stating that the allegations against him were serious in nature and that his release could hamper the ongoing investigation. The court also directed the Kerala High Court to consider Kappan's bail application afresh.

Lucknow trial court signed bail warrant for Kerala journalist Sidheeq Kappan on February 1, 2023. The court granted him bail and he was released from prison on the morning of February 2, 2023. In a release order signed by sitting judge Lucknow, the superintendent of Lucknow County Jail was instructed to release Kappan if he did not specifically want it after receiving a personal bond from him. The development came more than a month after he was granted bail by the Allahabad High Court in connection with a lawsuit under the Anti-Money Laundering Act (PMLA).

More than a month after being granted bail by the Allahabad High Court in connection with a Money Laundering Law (PMLA) case, Kerala journalist Siddique Kappan has served more than two years in prison. After that, he was released from prison on February 02. The Lucknow hearing signed an order releasing him on bail after accepting his bail. He was initially arrested for fear of disturbing the public order, but then he and his fellow passengers were charged for creating community unrest and also attempting to disrupt social harmony following the Hathras mass rape murder.

Last September, the Supreme Court granted him bail on all other counts, but he could not be released from prison because the PMLA case was pending. In October 2022, the Lucknow Circuit Court denied his bail request in the PMLA case. However, in December 2022, the Allahabad High Court found that

Kappan's bank had no other transactions, other than allegations that Rs. 5,000 had been transferred to the bank account of a co-defendant (Atikur Rahman) and granted him bail. The account is still in the co-defendant's bank account.

A Timeline of the Case

The arrest

The victim of the Hathras gang rape case died on 29 September 2020. From that day on, he wanted to go to Hathras to report the gang rape and murder case. Since the Hathras issue gained so much public protests, conflicts and problems, he was scared to go all alone by himself. So, he decided to take some other journalists too with him. They set out to Hathras from Delhi on 5 October 2020. After an hour of journey by car, they were stopped at the toll plaza in Mathura. They were asked to show the identity cards and asked their reason for going to Hathras. He replied that he is a reporter and he wanted to report the gang rape case. Also, he said that they can go back if there is any issue. But instead, the police asked to go to the police station to question them. As he said, no questioning was done from 10.30 am to 5.30 pm that day. They were just asked to wait. Later, a policeman came and asked who among them was the journalist from Kerala. Sidhee Kappan said it was him.

Later he saw agencies like military intelligence showing up. They were questioned till early morning the next day. Then they were taken in a car which had a BJP flag on it; it was not a police vehicle. They were presented before the Sub Divisional Magistrate and only then did they get to know about the charges against them. They were charged with disturbing the peace and inciting riots between religious groups. They were told to sign on an empty sheet of paper. Bail was not granted on personal bond despite their request. Then they were locked up in a quarantine center in a school in Mathura.

He was unable to contact his family. His phone, laptop and notepad were taken away. It was after 45 days that he talked to his family.

A UP Government Affidavit stated:

"Sidhee Kappan was going to Hathras under the garb of journalism with a very determined design to create a caste divide and disturb law and order situation and was found carrying incriminating material. "

But he said that the materials he carried with him were his laptop, phone, notepad and two pens which they might be stating as incriminating. He used to write articles on Unlawful Activities Prevention Act (UAPA), the people in India who were arrested on charges of UAPA, their detention period, etc. This was there on his laptop. And finally he himself got charged under UAPA.

He came to know about this only from the newspaper. He was directly informed by the police. He wasn't aware of this particular charge against him.

Jail Experience

For the first 21 days, they were in the quarantine center of a school. Around 50 prisoners were locked up in a classroom with no toilet facilities. They had to fight to use toilets. Even in the extreme conditions of the pandemic, they were just given a bucket to urinate on and too to the entire 50 prisoners. No phone call was permitted.

Later they were moved to the Mathura jail. And after 45 days, when he got a chance to speak to his family, he was denied to talk in malayalam. He was only allowed to speak either in Hindi or in English. When he requested badly to talk to his ill mother in malayalam just for minutes, only then he was permitted to speak in malayalam because his mother neither knew hindi nor english. This restriction was just laid upon him because he was the only one from Kerala.

During the initial days, other prisoners also believed the fake news that came about him in the media. He stated that Hindi media only gave out the police version, but not the truth. Later on, the truth came out and then the prisoners realized his innocence.

After the Delhi riots of 2020, two Malayalam news channels, Asianet News and Media One were banned by the home ministry for forty-eight hours. The government alleged that they had indulged in misreporting, against the government. Sidheeq Kappan sat against this ban in Jantar Mantar for a protest. He was the secretary of the Kerala Union of working Journalists of Delhi unit then. So, he led the protest. There were many protesters including politicians and other Delhi based journalists. But still, since Kappan was leading the protest, he was then in the hit list. So, even before the Hathras incident, he was targeted by right-wing politicians. They claimed that he was the mastermind of the Delhi riot.

UP special task force filed a 5000- page long chargesheet against Kappan which said:

"Sidheeq Kappan did not write like a responsible journalist and he writes only and only to incite Muslims, which is a hidden agenda of Popular Front of India (PFI). He wrote to sympathize with Maoists and Communists. He used to write anti-Hindu stories in Malayalam media to inflame the Delhi riots."

What is Ideal Media Freedom?

Media freedom refers to the concept that everyone, as individuals and members of organizations, has the right to voice their opinions and transmit information without being censored or interfered with by the government or any other entity. An ideal media freedom is one where individuals and organizations can practice this freedom without any hindrance

or government intervention. The topic of media freedom has gained a firm recognition as one of the essential human rights by many international bodies among them the United Nations. According to the Universal Declaration of Human Rights, everybody has the right to freedom of opinion and expression, which includes the freedom to hold any opinion without any interference and to directly or through any media to seek, receive, and impart information and

ideas regardless of frontiers.

In an ideal world, media freedom should be honored by all authorities and entities. The media need to have the autonomy to produce news content without any of the influences, censorship or limitations. Journalists and media professionals should, for instance, be able to report and publish their stories without any fear of persecution, harassment, or violence.

An ideal media freedom is, certainly, the safeguarding of journalists, and other media workers. They must be left alone to do their work without fear of any kind of repercussions such as physical.

Conclusion

The arrest and detention of Sidheeq Kappan, a journalist, highlights the balance between national security concerns and the right to free speech. This case study reveals the major legal and ethical dilemmas faced by India, showing how oppressive laws like Unlawful Activities (Prevention) Act (UAPA), could be misused to stifle criticism and curtail media freedom. In addition to individual rights, Kappan's case raises issues regarding press freedom in democracies and measures adopted for safeguarding journalists from unlawful arrests and harassment. Although national security is fundamental, there should be a balance with democratic values as well as human rights. The judiciary has an essential role in defending these rights, with this instance illustrating that abuse must be prevented by having a comprehensive legal mechanism. It also needs more openness as well as accountability in law enforcement operations. As such, this arrest of Sidheeq Kappan cautions against the fragility of free expression; hence demanding immediate reforms to ensure that legislations designed for protecting national security do not implicate government dissenters.

Findings of the Study

- There are very serious anti- democratic issues in India and people's views are least valued.

- India is becoming a hotbed of communal violence where people fight on religious lines and hurt others from other communities.
- Journalist safety in India has been a cause for concern over the years with cases of violence, harassment or intimidation being reported from different parts of the country.
- The increase of religious conflicts has become an issue in India whereby communal violence and religious intolerance have increased. This has led to a hindrance to individual freedom as people are afraid to freely voice their opinions and beliefs because they may be persecuted.

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